

Can a Polymeric Fiber Crack a Refractory Castable? On the Role of Microcracking on the Permeability Enhancement of Castables with Polymeric Fibers

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ABSTRACT

Hydraulic bonded refractories can be prone to explosive spalling during its heating process if the rate of mass transfer towards the environment is insufficient to counterbalance the vapor generation within the pores of the castable. In that case, the complex interaction of evaporation, pressurization and thermal gradients can lead to mechanical loads that surpasses the material's strength. One of the most common approaches adopted to mitigate the likelihood of facing explosions during water removal is by using polymeric fibers as drying additives, which have the role of increasing the material's intrinsic permeability. Although their effectiveness has been widely evaluated by both empirical laboratory observations and their widespread successful use in the industry, the underlying mechanism responsible for this mass transport improvement remains unknown. Thus, to leverage the latest advances in polymer science and engineering, and to unlock more effective, cheaper, or even greener options, it is a key aspect to critically evaluate the existing hypothesis that tries to explain the effectiveness of these drying additives. Thus, the current work investigates the proposed microcracking mechanism, which describes that the thermal expansion mismatch between the refractory castable and the polymer is responsible for the creation of cracks that act as microchannels capable of improving the percolation of the moisture through the refractory. Thermomechanical calculations were carried out for systems comprising different polymers including polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate and polyamide. The results revealed unexpectedly large mechanical stresses arising from the differential thermal expansion. Although the current findings do not conclusively validate the microcracking hypothesis, they highlight that this aspect should not be overlooked when selecting potential polymer candidates for drying additives. These insights provide a starting point for advancing the polymer selection strategies to optimize the refractory castable drying process.

INTRODUCTION

Refractory castables are a unique class of materials which can be shaped *in situ* into complex geometries, without the need for prior shaping or heat treatment¹. This capability offers great potential for reducing carbon dioxide emissions when castables are used as alternatives to pre-fired shaped products².

However, this possible advantage of this class of materials is hindered by the long dry out stage required especially by the hydraulic bonded castables to avoid any risk of facing explosive spalling³.

Consequently, several strategies have been developed to reduce the likelihood of the trapped moisture pressurization within the castable pores, which is believed to be a key component on the explosive phenomenon⁴.

One of the most commonly adopted approaches in the industry is to enhance the material's permeability by incorporating additives, such as polymeric fibers³. Salomão et

al. have demonstrated that physical transformations on these high aspect-ratio discontinuities led to a significant increase in air flow rate in compositions comprising these additives, when compared to reference compositions without them, as measured using a high temperature permeameter⁵.

In addition, the correlation between the fibers' melting point and the temperature at which the permeability increased observed in this study led to the hypothesis that the fibers shrunk and that the melting of the fibers enabled channels to be formed within the viscous melt, increasing the connectivity of already existing high permeable regions within the castable, such as the interfacial transition zone⁵.

Although, polymeric fibers indeed contract in length upon heating – due to the relaxation of strain induced crystallites originated during their drawing⁶ – the total volumetric change is positive, as shown in the specific volume versus temperature curve for polypropylene (PP) in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Specific volume as a function of temperature for PP. Adapted from He et al.⁷.

Thus, when investigating the effect of polymeric fibers in Portland cement concrete using scanning electron microscopy, Zhang et al. have proposed that the observed microcracks were originated by the mismatch between the thermal expansion of the concrete's matrix and the fibers, and that it was these cracks that formed a network and increased the permeability⁸. Although the authors attempted to measure the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fibers in their axial direction and correlate it with results from explosion tests, these observations did not yield definitive conclusions as the origins of such cracks could be related to the sample preparation, or even cooling of the sample.

Moreover, the Young modulus of polymers are in general more than two orders of magnitude smaller than the ones found out in castables and concrete⁹, and they also exhibit a viscoelastic behavior, which could provide mechanisms for the stress relaxation of the constrained thermal expansion, and

after reaching their melting point, they can start to deform through viscous flow.

In summary, Mohammed et al. described that the current state of understanding of the mechanisms behind the effectiveness of polymeric fibers, both as an additive to promote faster drying or to reduce the susceptibility of Portland cement concrete structures to fire damage, is not clear yet¹⁰.

Therefore, the present study aims to critically assess the microcracking mechanism hypothesis by using thermomechanical calculations to predict the upper limit of the maximum stresses that develop at the interface between the castable and the fibers. Five different polymers were assessed: i) linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE), ii) ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE), iii) polypropylene (PP), iv) polyethylene terephthalate, and v) polyamide 6,6, all considered within a matrix of calcium aluminate cement castable.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Given the complexity of all the processes which take place during the drying of concrete, the current work assumes a series of simplifications to enable a first quantitative analysis of the tangential stresses developed in the interface between the castable and the fibers. The focus on this component of the stress state is justified as this is the main responsible for the fracturing on the radial direction as described in Figure 2 a).

First, it is assumed that the fibers are perfectly dispersed within the castable and that the distance between each fiber is enough to prevent that the stress and strain fields between each fiber interacts among themselves.

Secondly, the geometry assumed is a 2D plane stress condition, that represents an infinitely long fiber with radius of 20 μm . Next, both the castable and the polymers are supposed to behave as perfectly elastic materials, which is an assumption that leads this set of results as being an upper limit of the maximum stresses that can be developed in this scenario. Also, because of this, the simulations finish at the polymers' melting point.

Finally, the material properties are assumed from the literature and the thermal expansion of the polymers are calculated from the specific volume versus density curves. The list of references for each property considered in this work is listed in Table I.

Tab. I: Mechanical properties considered in the model.

Material	E(T)	$\alpha(T)$	ν
LLDPE	Rocha et al.	Capt et al.	van Krevelen et al.
UHMWPE	Sanchez et al.	Heidari et al.	Yun et al.
PP	Wang et al.	He et al.	van Krevelen et al.
PET	Panowicz et al.	He et al.	van Krevelen et al.
PA 6,6	Belyamini et al.	He et al.	van Krevelen et al.
SCAC	Auvray et al.	Auvray et al.	Qi et al.

*References are provided as DOI hyperlinks in the table to respect the proceeding's page limits.

The thermomechanical analytical model is based on the work by Zago et al.¹¹, where the radial displacement, u_r , is given by Equation 1, and the geometry is depicted in Figure

$$u_r(r) = Ar + \frac{B}{r} \quad (1)$$

2.

The parameters A and B are calculated by the elastic constants and thermomechanical properties of the materials and have particular values for the fiber and the matrix as described in more details in the reference¹¹. Python scripts were developed to solve these equations.

Fig. 2: a) Geometry considered in the thermomechanical analytical model, radial and tangential stresses components, σ_{rr} and $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, respectively, and resulting radial crack, b) cylindrical system of coordinates. Adapted from Zago et al.¹¹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table II summarizes the physical properties of the polymers (the melting point, T_m , and the thermal strain at that temperature, ϵ_T), the maximum tangential stress predicted in the thermomechanical model, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max}$, and whether the body survived without damage (\checkmark) or not (\times) during a unidirectional heating test as reported by Zhang et al.¹².

Tab. II: Summary of properties and thermomechanical results.

Material	T_m [°C]	$\epsilon_T(T_m)$ [-]	$\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max}$ [MPa]	Survived in Zhang et al. ¹²
LLDPE	125	0.10	8.5	\times
UHMWPE	145	0.28	12.3	\times
PP	165	0.21	49.9	\checkmark
PET	260	0.36	25.4	\times
PA 6,6	260	0.21	54.0	\checkmark

It is clear that there is no direct correlation between the melting point, nor the thermal expansion alone, with the resistance against explosive spalling, as both the samples comprising LLDPE and PET, which had the minimum and maximum melting points, were both prone to damages in the experimental test proposed by Zhang et al.¹².

Moreover, the samples that did survive the heating test (with PP and PA 6,6), were the ones in which the thermomechanical analysis predicted the largest tangential stress, which might suggest that the microcrack hypothesis could partially explain the results in this set of analysis.

In order to better analyze these thermomechanical results and the differences in the behavior of the castable compositions with different polymer types, Table III presents

the radial displacement for each composition at the fiber's melting point.

Tab. III: Radial displacement for each composition.

Material	$u_r(r = 20\mu\text{m})$	$u_r(r = 80\mu\text{m})$
	[μm]	[μm]
LLDPE	0.03	0.10
UHMWPE	0.04	0.12
PP	0.08	0.15
PET	0.08	0.24
PA 6,6	0.11	0.25

The matrix displacement induced by the heating further away from the fiber ($r = 80\mu\text{m}$) is directly proportional to the final temperature of the simulation, as the matrix expansion is larger for PET and PA 6,6, which have the melting point of 260°C.

However, at the regions surrounding the interface between the fiber and the matrix ($r = 20\mu\text{m}$), the radial displacement was limited small values.

This is an effect of the constraint imposed by the smaller thermal expansion of the surrounding castable in comparison to the fiber. Consequently, large stresses are expected to be induced at this region, depending on how intense the stiffness degradation with the temperature increase is. Table IV shows the distribution of the tangential stress component in the matrix.

Tab. IV: Tangential stress at the fibers' melting point.

Material	$\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r = 20\mu\text{m})$	$\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r = 80\mu\text{m})$
	[MPa]	[MPa]
LLDPE	8.5	0.5
UHMWPE	12.3	0.7
PP	49.9	3.1
PET	25.7	1.6
PA 6,6	57.2	3.6

For all fibers, the maximum tangential stresses were observed right at the interface between the castable and the polymer ($r = 20\mu\text{m}$), as expected. Because of these large positive stresses, such regions are indeed susceptible to radial cracks, as the ones observed on the SEM micrographs by Zhang et al.⁸

The combination of larger thermal expansions and less intense stiffness degradation with increasing temperatures resulted in the highest observed stresses for PP and PA 6,6.

However, assuming that the microcracking is indeed the mechanism that leads to the observed permeability enhancement in the castables, the moment when the fracture takes place is also critical. If this microcracking only occurs at higher temperatures, the pressurization damage could already have taken place, or even worse, could be concurrent with the microcracking, which could reduce the castable strength and increase the likelihood of facing explosive spalling.

Thus, Table V presents the evolution of the tangential stresses as a function of the temperature. The polymers could be split into two groups based on their stresses. The first one, comprising LLDPE, UHMWPE and PET, exhibited tangential stresses below 25 MPa throughout all the simulation. In contrast, the second group - PP and PA 6,6 - exceeded this threshold even before 120°C, and reached

stresses in the tangential direction of almost 40 MPa at 150°C.

Tab. V: Evolution of the tangential stress at the interface between fiber and matrix with the temperature. The vapor pressure calculated by Antoine's (P_{Ant}) equation is also presented. All values are in MPa.

Material	50°C	100°C	150°C	200°C
LLDPE	4.2	7.5	-	-
UHMWPE	2.6	6.9	-	-
PP	9.5	21.2	39.5	-
PET	3.7	16.4	21.5	23.3
PA 6,6	13.1	31.0	39.2	46.8
P_{Ant}	0.01	0.1	0.48	1.55

This temperature is of practical interest as it is after this point that the water vapor pressure increases considerably, as predicted by the Antoine's equation, also highlighted in Table V.

Thus, when considering the results of the explosion tests conducted by Zhang et al. and shown in Table II, the predicted tangential stresses could indeed be correlated with the resistance of these materials against the explosive spalling. However, in order to have clear conclusions, methods capable of directly observing the formation of microcracks during the drying are critical, as other aspects need to be considered such as the possibility of the polymer melting infiltrating the cracks, or even that the crack mouth is not wide enough to promote viable paths for moisture transfer within the castable structure, as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Schematic representation of the mean free path, λ , requirement to enable mass transfer through an aperture of size d , when a) the crack is too small, b) when it is large enough to enable mass transfer.

Nonetheless, the current findings highlight that the thermomechanical stresses induced by the mismatch of thermal expansion between fibers and the castable matrix are not negligible and should be considered, even if other still unknown mechanisms are present in the permeability evolution behavior of refractory monolithics comprising polymeric fibers.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The thermomechanical analysis presented in this study indicated that the thermal expansion mismatch between polymeric fibers and the castable matrix can generate significant tangential stresses at the interface, potentially leading to microcracking.

Among the evaluated polymers, polypropylene (PP) and polyamide 6,6 (PA 6,6) were associated with the highest tangential stresses, which correlates with experimental observations where these fibers enhanced the castable's resistance to explosive spalling. This supports, at least partially, the hypothesis that microcracking plays a role in the permeability enhancement mechanism provided by polymeric fibers.

However, the occurrence of microcracks alone may not be sufficient to ensure effective moisture transport. The temperature of cracking, their connectivity to the pore network, and whether the crack aperture meets the critical threshold for vapor flow are all decisive factors.

Furthermore, the possibility of the molten polymer infiltrating and sealing these cracks, or the viscoelastic relaxation mitigating the induced stresses, adds additional complexity to this process.

Nonetheless, these results demonstrate that the differential thermal expansion of the fibers should be further investigated to provide the complete understanding of permeability enhancement in fiber containing castables.

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